

STRESS MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES USED BY KWARA STATE COLLEGE OF EDUCATION STUDENTS, ILORIN, KWARA STATE

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ABSTRACT

This study was carried out to investigate stress management strategies used by Kwara State College of Education students, Ilorin, Kwara State. Kwara State College of Education students are faced with series of stressful challenges from academic stress to psychological stress, difficulty in lectures comprehension, poor students-lecturer relationship, student-student relationship, inability to identify their stressor, and negative coping techniques is used to manage their stress which harm their health. The purpose of this study was to: Investigate the use of relaxation and seeking spiritual support as a stress management strategy by Kwara State College of Education student in Ilorin. Descriptive research of the survey type was adopted for this study. Multi-stage sampling technique of cluster, simple random and purposive sampling techniques was used to select four hundred and two (402) respondents from the five schools in the Kwara State College of education. A researcher developed structured questionnaire was used for this study and validated by three (3) experts in the Department of Health Promotion and Environmental Health Education, Faculty of Education, University of Ilorin. A reliability co-efficient, $r=0.84$ was obtained through split-half method. Data collection was conducted by the researcher and three trained research assistants. Inferential statistics of Chi-square (χ^2) was used to analyze the null hypotheses at 0.05 alpha level. The findings of the study show that: Relaxation was significantly used by Kwara State College of Education students, Ilorin as stress management strategy because calculated chi-square value 263.85 is greater than chi-square table value 9.48 (Cal χ^2 val > Tab χ^2 val). Seeking spiritual support was significantly used by Kwara State College of Education students, Ilorin as stress management strategy because calculated chi-square value 211.64 is greater than chi-square table value 9.48 (Cal χ^2 val > Tab χ^2 val). Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that Kwara State College of Education students, Ilorin, Kwara State, should be encouraged to continue because they used relaxation, spiritual support and seek diversion as stress management strategies. Therefore, the following recommendations were suggested; Kwara State College of Education governing council should set up different recreational centers in the school, religious leaders in the institution should constantly orientate students on spiritual tips to manage their stressful event.

INTRODUCTION

Stress is the emotional and physical strain caused by our response to pressure from the outside world. It is specific response by the body to a stimulus that disturbs normal functioning. A stressor is an event or any stimulus that caused an individual to experience stress

(Basavanthappa, 2004). It is almost impossible to live without some stress and most of us would not want to, because it gives life some spice and excitement. But if stress gets out of control, it may harm health, your relationship and your enjoyment of life. Stress has been defined as the body nonspecific response to

demands made upon it, or to disturbing events in the environment, thus it is not just a stimulus or a response, but rather a process by which we perceived and cope with environmental threats and challenges (Sami-Abdo, 2011).

However, to understand one's stress, Blona (2005) pointed out that one needs to know what it is and its causes, in order to cope with it well. The author defined stress as any event or circumstances that strained or exceeds an individual ability to cope. It is a fact that when people come together, stress is bound to happen one way or the other. Akinboye(2002) described stress as the body's response to any undesirable mental, physical, emotional, social or environmental demand. Akinade (2005) also defined stress as a pattern of cognitive appraisal, physiological responses and behavioral tendencies that occurred in a response to a perceived imbalance between situational demands and the resources needed to cope with them. It is something that occurred when people are faced with events they perceived as endangering their physical or psychological well being.

Omoniyi (2000) classified stressors into social stressors, emotional stressors, physical stressor, and environmental stressors among others

which are related to the study. However, higher levels of stress were reported as arising from funding cuts to universities, heavier teaching loads, difficulty in securing research funds, lack of resources, poor relationships with colleagues and unrealistic expectations from management (Winefield & Jarret, 2001). Stress can be destructive if not well managed. In addition to its effect on the health of the student, it also has direct bearing on the students' performance and productivity. On the basis of this, it is important that every occurrence of stress be properly managed to ensure that such negative effects are minimized if not eliminated. This can be best achieved by adopting appropriate mechanisms (Awopegba, 2001).

Wells-Moran (2006) defined coping strategies as the specific efforts, both behavioral and psychological, that people employed to master, tolerate, reduce, or minimize stressful events. The author classified coping strategies into problem-solving strategies which are efforts to do something active to alleviate stressful circumstances and emotion-focused coping strategies which involve efforts to regulate the emotional consequences of stressful or potentially stressful events. MacArthur (2014) further categorized coping strategies into active and avoidant coping strategies. Active coping strategies are either behavioral or psychological responses designed to change the

nature of the stressor itself or how one thinks about it, whereas avoidant coping strategies lead people into activities (such as alcohol use) or mental states (such as withdrawal) that keep them from directly addressing stressful events.

Relaxation is a conscious attempt to bring physiological changes and arousal of brain to normal level, it was found that extroverts' arousal level is significantly lower as compared to that of introverts, thus making introverts more prone to stress (Sharma, 2011). Unstructured leisure activities, such as hanging out, going to the mall, or watching movies, also appeared to play a role in adolescents positive coping with stress which are most beneficial when individuals engaged in activities that are positive, fulfilling, and of their choosing (Lazarus, 2006). Around the world, faith traditions are as deeply rooted as they are varied, if these roots help an individual feel grounded, a short repetitive prayer could be a good way to elicit the relaxation response (Seyedfatemi, 2007). When prayer is meaningful, the repetition of such a prayer can enhance the relaxation response and possibly your health as well, given body an inborn ability to heal itself. Believing in the healing power of mind-body approached and specifically in the power of the prayer chosen to aid (Hoge, 2010).

Statement of the Problem

Students are expected to receive lectures in conducive academic environment that is devoid of all sort of physical distractions, these may include easy transportation from home to schools, getting all the needed personal materials such as food, cloth, shoes, money among others. Similarly, students are expected to have excellence performance for completion of a particular course in a session. It is also important that there is smooth integration into the academic environment and good relationship between the students to the co-student and also between the students and their lecturers in a manner that will improve smooth teaching and learning process.

Students are faced with one stressful challenges or the other which include, difficulty in transportation, lack or insufficient materials e.g. cloth, books and shoes, difficulties in integrating into their academic environment, lack of companionship, occasion by isolation, discrimination and stigmatization, frustration from student to students, student to lecturers. The researcher intends to determine the different stress management strategies used by these college students in Ilorin Metropolis, Kwara State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were answered:

- i. Will relaxation be a stress management strategy used by Kwara State College of Education students?
- ii. Will seeking spiritual support be a stress management strategy used by Kwara State College of Education students?

Research Hypotheses

- i. Relaxation will not be significantly used by Kwara State College of Education students as a stress management strategy.
- ii. Seeking spiritual support will not be significantly used by Kwara State College of Education students as a stress management strategy.

Methodology

Descriptive research design of the survey type was adopted for this study. The population of the study were Kwara State College of Education students, Ilorin, Kwara State. Multi-stage sampling technique consisting of proportionate and purposive was used to select (402) respondents from the five schools/faculties in the College for the study. Purposive sampling technique was used to select Kwara State College of Education, Ilorin, Kwara State, purposive sampling techniques was used to select N.C.E III students from

all the five schools/faculties of the institution; School of Art and Social Sciences (158), School of Education (260), School of Language (222), School of Sciences (300), School of Vocational and Technical Education (233), making a total of 1341. Proportionate sampling was used to select thirty percent of the respondent, which give 402 in total.

The researcher developed structured questionnaire was used for this study. The instrument contained statements on stress management strategies used by Kwara State College of Education students, Ilorin, Kwara State. A two point Likert rating scale with alternative of Agree and Disagree was used. In order to ascertain the validity of the instrument used, three copies of the questionnaire were given to three experts in the Department of Health Promotion and Environmental Health Education, Faculty of Education, University of Ilorin. The split-half method was used to determine the reliability of the instrument using Cronbach alpha techniques to correlate the data. Co-efficient of $r=0.84$ alpha level using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 22.0.

Results

Research question one: Will relaxation be a stress management strategy used by Kwara State College of Education students, Ilorin, Kwara State?

Table 1: Relaxation as Stress Management Strategy used by Kwara State College of Education Student.

Table 1 shows the answer to research question one and it indicated 369 (91.8%) of respondents agreed that relaxation is one of the stress management strategy used by Kwara State College of Education students while 33 (8.2%) disagree with the opinion that relaxation can be used as a stress management strategy by Kwara State Colleges of Education students. 292 (72.6%) agreed that working on ones hobby is a method under relaxation as stress management strategy used by Kwara State College of Education students and 110 (27.4%) disagreed with the opinion. While 348 (86.6%) agreed that sleep is a method under relaxation as stress management strategy used by Kwara State College of Education students and 54 (13.4%) disagreed. Also, 140 (34.8%) agreed that muscle relaxation practice is a method under relaxation as stress management strategy used by Kwara State College of Education students and 262 (65.2%) disagreed with the opinion. Finally 273 (67.9%) agreed that deep breath is a method under relaxation as stress management strategy used by Kwara State College Education students and 129 (32.1%) disagreed with the opinion. This implies that relaxation is one of the stress management strategy used by Kwara State College of Education students, Ilorin, Kwara State.

Research Question Two: Will seeking

spiritual support be stress management strategy used by Kwara State College of Education students, Ilorin, Kwara State?

Table 2: Seeking Spiritual support as Stress Management Strategy used by Kwara State College of Education Students.

Table 2 shows the answer to research question two and it indicated 190 (47.3%) of the respondents agreed spiritual support is one of the stress management strategy used by Kwara State College of Education students, Ilorin and 212 (52.7%) disagreed. While 338 (84.1%) agreed that prayer is a method under seeking spiritual support as stress management strategy used by Kwara State College of Education students and 64 (15.9%) disagreed with the opinion. 326 (81.1%) agreed that reading Bible/ Quran is a method under spiritual support as stress management strategy used by Kwara State College of Education students and 76

S/No	ITEMS	AGREE %	DISAGREE %
1	I use relaxation as a stress management strategy	369 (91.8%)	33 (8.2%)
2	I work on my hobby when i am disturbed	292 (72.6%)	110 (27.4%)
3	I sleep when I am stressed.	348 (86.6%)	54 (13.4%)
4	I do practice muscle relaxation when I feel disturbed	140 (34.8%)	262 (65.2%)
5	I do deep breath when am stressed	273 (67.9%)	129 (32.1%)
\bar{X}		284 (70.4%)	118 (29.3%)

(18.9%) disagreed with the opinion. Also, 194 (48.3%) agreed that talking to cleric, pastor or priest is a method under spiritual support as stress management strategy used by Kwara State College of Education students and 208 (51.7%) disagreed. Finally, 179 (44.5%) agreed that visiting church/mosque is a method under spiritual as stress management strategy used by Kwara State Colleges of Education students and 223 (55.5%) disagreed with the opinion. This implies that seeking spiritual support is one of stress management strategy used by Kwara State College of Education students, Ilorin, Kwara State.

Hypotheses testing

Hypothesis one: Relaxation will not be significantly used by Kwara State College of Education students, Ilorin, Kwara State as a stress management strategy.

Table 4: Chi-Square Result Showing Relaxation as a Stress Management Strategy used by Kwara State College of Education Students.

Table 4 shows result of the tested hypothesis one which stated relaxation would not be significantly used by Kwara State College of Education students, Ilorin as stress management strategy. The calculated chi-square value 263.85 is greater than chi-square table value of 9.48 ($Cal \chi^2 val > Tab \chi^2 val$), Hypothesis one is therefore rejected and this implies that relaxation was significantly used by Kwara State College of Education students, Ilorin as stress management strategy.

Hypothesis two: Seeking spiritual support will not be significantly used by Kwara State College of Education students, Ilorin, Kwara State as stress management strategy.

Table 5: Chi-Square Result showing Seeking spiritual Support as a Stress management Strategy used by Kwara State College of Education Students. Table five shows result of the tested hypothesis two Seeking spiritual support would not be significantly

used by Kwara State College of Education students, Ilorin as stress management strategy. The calculated chi-square value 211.64 is greater than chi-square table value of 9.48 (Cal χ^2 val > Tab χ^2 val), the hypothesis is therefore rejected and this implies that Seeking spiritual support was significantly used Kwara State College of Education students in Ilorin as stress management strategy.

Discussion of findings

Hypothesis one stated that relaxation will not be significantly used by Kwara State College of Education students in Ilorin. Kwara State as stress management strategy. The finding from the study revealed that relaxation was significantly used by Kwara State College of Education student as stress management strategy. This is similar to the finding of Bickford (2005) explained that stress can also be prevented by practicing relaxation. Relaxation is able to calm student psychological and physiological states of mind. Students who are psychologically relaxed feel peaceful, in control and experience less stress and anxiety. Physiological relaxation required students to do muscle relaxation, relaxation response, autogenic training and relaxation imagery, it was mentioned that relaxation is the best stress management technique which can prevent stress at the workplace. Employees can also exercise other relaxation techniques such as doing

yoga, listening to music and meditate.

Hypothesis two seeking spiritual support will not be significantly used by Kwara State College of Education students, Ilorin, Kwara State as stress management strategy. The finding from the study revealed that Kwara State College of education student in Ilorin used spiritual support as stress management strategy this finding is related to Arnetz (2014) suggested that, spiritual practices are efficient coping mechanism for students who are over loaded and these practices ultimately protect students from exhausting, if students incorporate their spiritual/religious values in institution then these can definitely help them in promoting mental well-being and attenuating institution stress.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that Kwara State College of Education students manage their stress effectively and encouragement they should be encourage to continue because;

- i. Kwara State College of Education students, Ilorin, Kwara State, used relaxation as stress management strategy, work on their hobby, sleep, practice muscle relaxation and deep breath when stressed. Because the cal value (263.85) > critical value (9.48).
- ii. Kwara State College of Education students, Ilorin, Kwara State, used spiritual support as

S/ N	ITEMS	AGREE %	DISAGREE %	Row Total	Df	Cal χ^2	Tab χ^2	Decision
1	I use relaxation as a stress management strategy	369 (91.8%)	33 (8.2%)	402				
2	I work on my hobby when i am disturbed	292 (72.6%)	110 (27.4%)	402				
3	I sleep when I am stressed.	348 (86.6%)	54 (13.4%)	402	4	263.85	9.48	Ho rejected
4	I do practice muscle relaxation when I feel disturbed	140 (34.8%)	262 (65.2%)	402				
5	I deep breath when am stressed	273 (67.9%)	129 (32.1%)	402				
\bar{X}		284 (70.4%)	118 (29.3%)					

$\alpha = 0.05$

S/N	ITEMS	AGREE %	DISAGREE %	Row Total	Df	Cal χ^2	Tab χ^2	Decision
6	I use spiritual support as a stress management strategy	190 (47.3%)	212 (52.7%)	402				
7	I pray when I am nervous.	338 (84.1%)	64 (15.9%)	402				
8	I read Bible/Quran when I am disturbed.	326 (81.1%)	76 (18.9%)	402	4	211.64	9.48	Ho rejected
9	I talk to cleric, pastor or priest when I am confused.	194 (48.3%)	208 (51.7%)	402				
10	I visit church/mosque when I am angry.	179 (44.5%)	223 (55.5%)	402				
\bar{X}		245 (61.1%)	157 (38.9%)					

$\alpha = 0.05$

stress management strategy, pray, read Bible/Quran, talk to cleric or pastor and visit church or mosque when stressed. Because the cal χ^2 value (211.64) > critical value (9.48).

freely accessed.

- ii. Religious leaders in the institution should constantly orientate students on various spiritual tips to manage their stressful events.

Recommendations

Based on the findings the following recommendations were made:

- i. Kwara State College of Education governing council should set up different recreational centers in the institution in which students can

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